

Studies on Dithiocarbamates: Part II. Ultraviolet Absorption Spectra of Tetrahydro-1,3,5-Thiadiazine-2-Thiones.

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Ultraviolet absorption spectra of 3:5-dialkyl-, 3:5-diaryl-, 3-phenyl-5-alkyl- and 3-aryl-5-methyl tetrahydrothiadiazine-2-thiones have been examined. Each group is found to display a characteristic pattern with $\lambda_{\max}$ around 250 and 290 m μ . An attempt has been made to explain band positions in terms of N and S conjugation.

The dithiocarbamates are known to have profound effect on biological system, and this has provoked considerable activity in various derivatives of dithiocarbamates or in compounds incorporating the same functional moiety. Our interest¹ in the field of dithiocarbamates, therefore, led us to examine the potential use of some tetrahydro-1, 3, 5-thiadiazine-2-thiones (II), various derivatives of which have been claimed^{2,4,5} to be useful fungicides, herbicides, nematocides and so on.

Ainley and his co-workers³ first made systematic investigation on the mode of formation of tetrahydro-1,3,5-thiadiazines and correctly interpreted their structure, mainly, on the basis of similarity of their absorption spectra with dithiocarbamates. More recently, various derivatives of tetrahydro-1,3,5-thiadiazine-2-thiones, (II) have been reported^{4,5,6}. Nevertheless a check on published information revealed considerable amount of confusion regarding m.p.s. of identical compounds (see table I). As authentic compounds were needed for our work, it was decided to establish identity of some compounds already reported by others^{3,4,5,6} by measuring and comparing the ultraviolet absorption characteristics. Feasibility of this approach was already indicated by the work of Ainley and his co-workers³; but to our knowledge, systematic investigation on 3, 5-disubstituted tetrahydro-1,3,5-thiadiazine-2-thiones(II) is still lacking.

1. Talukdar, *Ind. J. Appl. Chem.*, 1965, **28**, 197.
2. Davies & Sexton, *Biochem. J.*, 1949, **43**, 461;
Yoder, U.S. Pat., 2,838, 389 (1958)/*Chem. Abstr.*, 1958, **52**, 20864.
3. Ainley et al., *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 144.
4. Rieche et al., *Arch. Pharm.*, 1960, **293**, 957.
5. Takubo & Tadaoka, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1964, **61**, 4357.
6. Shah and Trivedi, *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **41**, 225.

The following types of compounds were selected for our study: (a) 3:5-dialkyl-, (b) 3:5-diaryl-, (c) 3-phenyl-5-alkyl-, and (d) 3-aryl-5-methyltetrahydro-1, 3, 5-thiadiazine-2-thiones. However, as we were more concerned with gross absorption pattern which could be attributed to the type of substituents, the number of compounds has been restricted, in some cases, to bare minimum. Attempt was also made to examine the effect of electron donating or electron-withdrawing group in the aryl substituents.

The compounds investigated here were all made by standard methods^{4,5}. In the case of compounds (c) and (d), prior formation and isolation of the intermediate dithiocarbamate salt (I) gave a purer product. Further, thermal sensitivity of the compounds (II), mainly, 3-phenyl-5-alkyl types, made it imperative to use minimum amount of heating during purification by crystallisation. Relevant data are summarised in Table I and their absorption data are assembled in Table II.

EXPERIMENTAL

Spectral measurements were made with freshly prepared solutions of substances in methanol in Hilger UVI-spek with matched 1 c.m. quartz cell. M.p.s. were determined in open capillary and are uncorrected.

Preparation of 3:5-Dialkyl/Diaryltetrahydro-1,3,5-thiadiazine-2-thione (II, R=R').—A solution of 0.02 mole of the amine in ethanol (30 ml.) was cooled to about 20°, then 0.01 mole of carbon disulphide was added. The mixture was stirred at 30-35° for about 3 hr. and again cooled to about 10°; 0.02 mole formaldehyde (as 38% w/v solution) was then added dropwise. After addition of formaldehyde, stirring was continued at 30-35° for 3 hr. more when the product usually separated as a solid or semisolid. The semisolid on trituration with little more ethanol gave white crystalline material. These were cautiously crystallised from appropriate solvents with minimum amount of heating.

Preparation of 3-Aryl-5-alkyltetrahydro-1,3,5-thiadiazine-2-thione (II, R=aryl, R'=alkyl).—5ml. of conc. ammonia solution (d, 0.88) was added dropwise, to a cold (about 15°) solution containing 0.01 mole amine and 0.01 mole carbon disulphide in 20 ml. of ethanol. The mixture was stirred in cold for 1 hr., then at 30-35° for 2 hr. more. The precipitated salt was collected and washed with little ether and immediately used for the subsequent reaction.

An aqueous or aqueous-alcoholic solution of the above salt was diluted to about 250 ml. with ice-cold water, filtered, and the filtrate was cooled to about 10°; 0.01 mole of alkylamine sulphate was then added with agitation. After another 10 min, 0.02 mole of formaldehyde (as 38% w/v solution) was added dropwise. The mixture was stirred in cold for 30 min, then for 3 hr. more at 30-35° when the products usually separated as white crystalline material. These were collected, washed with cold water and then purified in the usual way.

Since attention was directed towards isolation of pure material, no attempt was made to ascertain the yield.

A mixture of aromatic and aliphatic amines may be directly treated with carbon disulphide and formaldehyde to get the desired 3-aryl-5-alkyl type of compounds, but the above method was found to give easily crystallisable product.

DISCUSSION

The dithiocarbamates in general show two fairly strong bands at 250 μ and 290 μ regions (with $\log \epsilon$ about 4) and a weak band around 330-360 μ region. The former two bands were attributed to N-conjugation and S-conjugation respectively by Koch⁷. But Janssen⁸ reversed these assignments on the basis of his exhaustive studies on dithiocarbamates and related compounds. Further, an important point arising out of his theoretical calculations is the participation of S d-orbital in the excited state. These two possible types of transitions may be represented as in III and IV.

As expected, we noted two bands in 210-320 μ region (see Table II), but each group of compounds displayed distinctive absorption pattern as discussed below. In figure I, the characteristic pattern of a representative member of each group is illustrated.

(a) 3:5-dialkyl-II.—In these cases, (nos. 1-3, Table II), the compounds bearing identical groups in 3 and 5 positions show a typical absorption curve where the 290 μ band is fairly stronger than the 250 μ band.

(b) 3:5-diaryl-II (nos. 4-6, Table II).—Replacement of alkyl by aryl groups was found to enhance the intensities of both bands, but in all cases 250 μ band is remarkably stronger than 290 μ band. With powerful electron donating group in the *para* position of the aryl group, the hyperchromic effect in the 250 μ band is very significant. In other words, the gross pattern is reversed in switching over from 3:5-dialkyl to 3:5 di-aryl type.

(c) 3-Phenyl-5-alkyl-II (nos., 7-11, Table II). In these instances the band intensities at 250 μ and 290 μ were of the same order of magnitude with 290 μ band being slightly stronger than 250 μ band. Apart from minor variation in position and intensity of the bands (at 250 μ or 290 μ), there is hardly any significant trend which could be attributed to change in N-5 alkyl group. In fact, the absorption pattern is reminiscent of an open chain N,N-dialkyl dithiocarbamate ester.

(d) 3-aryl-5-Methyl-II (nos., 7,12-14, Table II).—In 3-phenyl-5-methyl compound (no.7, Table II), intensities of both bands are of the same order of magnitude, 290 μ band being slightly stronger than the 250 μ band. But the presence of electron donating group in *para* position of 3-phenyl was found to intensity the 250 μ band more than the 290 μ band and a slight shift of $\lambda_{\max}$ towards shorter wavelength is also noticeable.

7. Koch, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 401.

8. Janssen, *Res. Trav. Chim.*, 1960, 79, 454, 464, 1068.

TABLE I

3:5-disubstituted tetrahydro-1,3,5-thiadiazine-2-thione

Sl. No.	R	R'	m.p. O.	Reported m.p. (ref.)	Mol. Formula	%N	
						Req.	Found
1.	Methyl	Methyl	106 ^a	106(3)	C ₉ H ₁₀ N ₂ S ₂	17.28	17.19
2.	Cyclohexyl	Cyclohexyl	149-150 ^a	151(4)	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ N ₂ S ₂	9.30	9.66
3.	Benzyl	Benzyl	103 ^b	101-102(4); 102(6)	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₂ S ₂	8.91	8.85
4.	Phenyl	Phenyl	178 ^d	178(4); 140(6)	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₂ S ₂	9.79	9.49
5.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	132-133 ^b	206(6)	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₂ S ₂	8.91	8.68
6.	<i>p</i> -Phenetyl	<i>p</i> -Phenetyl	158-159 ^c	159-60(4)	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ N ₂ S ₂ O ₂	7.48	7.52
7.	Phenyl	Methyl	142-143 ^b	148(3.6); 129(5)	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ N ₂ S ₂	12.94	12.55
8.	"	<i>n</i> -Propyl	125-126 ^b	110(5)	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ S ₂	11.11	11.32
9.	"	<i>n</i> -Butyl	114-115 ^d	101(6); 93(5)	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ N ₂ S ₂	10.52	10.62
10.	"	<i>n</i> -Hexyl	108-109 ^b	108(6); 83(5)	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ N ₂ S ₂	9.52	9.68
11.	"	Cyclohexyl	142-143 ^c	131(5)	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₂ S ₂	9.58	9.38
12.	<i>p</i> -tolyl	Methyl	131-132 ^b	117(6)	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₂ S ₂ ^h	11.76	11.76
13.	<i>p</i> -Phenetyl	"	163-164 ^c		C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ S ₂ O	10.44	10.58
14.	<i>p</i> -hydroxyphenyl	"	162-163 ^b	163-64 (3)	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ N ₂ S ₂ O	11.66	11.52

Crystd. from (a) acetone-hexane, (b) ethanol, (c) acetone and (d) benzene (g) Found: C, 58.93; H, 6.70. C₁₅H₁₈N₂S₂ requires C, 58.65; H, 6.76. (h) Found: C, 55.26; H, 5.95. C₁₁H₁₄N₂S₂ requires C, 55.46; H, 5.88.

TABLE II
UV absorption Data of II

Sl. No.	R	R'	λ_{max}		λ_{max}	
			m μ	ϵ	m μ	ϵ
1.	Methyl	Methyl	245	6,220	285	11,670
2.	Cyclohexyl	Cyclohexyl	254	8,670	291	12,910
3.	Benzyl	Benzyl	248	8,730	290	12,320
4.	Phenyl	Phenyl	247	15,320	294	10,070
5.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	247	18,720	292	10,820
6.	<i>p</i> -Phenetyl	<i>p</i> -Phenetyl	244	21,380	290	13,400
7.	Phenyl	Methyl	248	9,209	294	9,569
8.	"	<i>n</i> -Propyl	250	8,420	296	8,900
9.	"	<i>n</i> -Butyl	250	8,840	297	9,280
10.	"	<i>n</i> -Hexyl	250	9,480	291	9,690
11.	"	Cyclohexyl	251	9,840	294	11,320
12.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	Methyl	248	10,710	293	10,350
13.	<i>p</i> -Phenetyl	"	244	11,380	290	10,520
14.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	"	244	10,680	289	11,980

It is therefore reasonable to conclude that each of the four groups of tetrahydro-1, 3, 5-thiadiazine-2-thione exhibits characteristic absorption pattern which could be profitably used for identification.

FIG. 1

a, b, c & d refer to compound nos., 1, 6, 7 & 13 respectively in Table II.

Regarding assignment of bands to either *N*-conjugation (III) or *S*-conjugation (IV) it is worth while to compare the observed band intensities between (b) and (d) groups.

Whenever N_2 methyl is replaced by an aryl group, the resulting electronic perturbation is more reflected in the 250 $m\mu$ band. It is difficult to visualize such a significant change in terms of *N*-conjugation (III). This is in accord with the type of results obtained with compounds in group (c).

Further, Comparison of results of group (a) with those of group (c) and (d) indicates that replacement of N_2 -methyl/cyclohexyl (nos., 1, 2, Table II), by aryl group (nos. 7, 11, 12, 13, Table II) is accompanied by a red shift of λ_{max} (290 $m\mu$ band) with concomitant fall in ϵ values.

These results, therefore, strongly suggest that 250 $m\mu$ and 290 $m\mu$ bands are predominantly associated with *S*-conjugation (IV) and *N*-conjugation (III) respectively as found by Jenssen⁶; and plausibly indicates $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition. Moreover, participation of

d-orbital of sulphur with powerful electron-donating group at N_2 -aryl cannot be ruled out completely.

Another point of interest is the favourable disposition (1:3) of sulphur to both N_2 and N_3 . But in order to explain the spectroscopic data, it becomes necessary to assume nonplanar conformation, as shown in V, of the tetrahydro-1:3:5-thiadiazine-2-thione ring where unshared electrons of sulphur should be sterically closer to N_2 than N_3 . This concept finds its close analogy in the reported⁹ absorption characteristics of allyl alkyl sulphide (VI) where participation of unshared electrons of sulphur with π -electrons of allyl group has been assumed to occur as shown below.

Further studies are in progress for additional information.

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